

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most quite a few North American bears. The most common is the American black bear, followed by the brown bear and then the polar bear. Discovered all through Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Could be dark or light brown (cinnamon), generally even white. Not at all times black in shade. 900,000 and never threatened. □□ Location: The American black bear could be found throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Nonetheless, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected underneath the U.S. □□ Size: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to six ft in length. □□ Features: Most black bears are black, however their fur can range from dark brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on rare events. They've pointed ears and a straight face. Of all the bear species black bears are a few of the best at climbing bushes. Their comparatively smaller size and shorter claws make them fast and nimble to climb bushes for protection, food, and even hibernation. The majority of their food regimen is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Weight loss plan: Their assorted eating regimen provides them the power to dwell in a large vary of habitats. Additionally they eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Dangerous? They are the probably bear to be encountered within the backcountry. And yes, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the 2 subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are found within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Brown bears are the most widespread of all bear species, discovered in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Grizzlies are accountable for almost all bear assaults in North America, with 46 per 12 months. Though their conservation standing is "least concern", their spread-out nature and lowered habitat make most of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a wide variety of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a big build, a dish-formed face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the ideas, which led to the identify of probably the most famous subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and a few even hunt young mammals corresponding to elk and moose. Their coloration varies from light blonde to darkish brown. The two subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□ Location: Grizzly bears are found in the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Dimension: Adults weigh four hundred to 790 pounds, are 6.5 toes long, and have a shoulder height of 3. Three feet. □□ Eating regimen: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been known to prey on giant mammals. Coastal grizzlies are usually larger than those found in the Rocky Mountains because of a richer weight-reduction plan. Each year there are forty six assaults and 6 deaths. □□ Dangerous? Recognized for his or her aggressive conduct, grizzlies are accountable for essentially the most bear assaults in North America. □□ Location: Kodiak bears are only discovered on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Measurement: Kodiak bears are nearly as large as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1, four hundred pounds, eight toes long, and four ft tall at the shoulder. □□ Eating regimen: Their weight-reduction plan is just like mainland grizzly bears. Nonetheless, due to more plentiful food sources, the islands can assist a denser bear population. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to change into their very own subspecies. This has led to a more advanced social construction which results in much less battle between bears. □□ Harmful? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears could be aggressive. Due to their isolation, there is just one assault on people each other yr. Largest species of bear on the planet weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Weight loss plan is generally made up of meat, often from seals. □□ Location: Polar bears are the most important bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur seems white but is actually clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears vary within the snow-lined arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Size: Grownup polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and could be 7 to 10 feet tall. They're a threatened species as a consequence of loss of habitat from local weather change. Regardless of their enormous dimension polar bears might be quick, maintaining a 6 mph tempo in the water. □□ Options: Compared to other bears, polar bears have a slimmer body, narrow head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps gained Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph pace! □□ Eating regimen: Their weight loss plan consists mostly of animals, especially seals which they will smell from a mile away. Though they appear white, their fur is actually clear and their skin is black. □□ Harmful? Polar bears may be extraordinarily dangerous. They see people as potential prey. Attacks are uncommon as a result of distant nature of their habitat. Recognized for its cream colour chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of the smaller bears. Straightforward to tame and infrequently common in circuses. □□ Location: The Asian black bear is found in forests and shrublands across Asia from Iran to Japan. The inhabitants is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is taken into account vulnerable. □□ Dimension: One of many smaller species, adults weigh round 300 pounds and stand forty seven to 75 inches tall. □□ Food regimen: Relying on the season it commonly feeds on small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits,

berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Assaults on people are growing as individuals encroach on their habitat. □□ Dangerous? They're certainly one of the simplest bears to tame (and subsequently frequent in circuses), however Asian black bears are more aggressive than their North American counterparts. Discovered solely in China. 99% of its food regimen is bamboo. In truth, the second individual in historical past to obtain a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear while protecting his sheep. Recognized for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped physique. □□ Location: Pandas are found solely in China. Only 1,500 to 2,000 stay within the wild and they're considered a weak species. □□ Dimension: Pandas weigh around 300 pounds and may be over four ft tall, an impressive feat contemplating they weigh only about 3.5 ounces at beginning. It also has a detailed cousin, the Qinling panda which has the identical sample in mild brown and white. □□ Eating regimen: In contrast to different bears the panda's food plan is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. □□ Options: The giant panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped body. All that fibrous bamboo retains them regular: they poop over forty occasions a day! □□ Dangerous? Attacks are uncommon but harmful, on condition that pandas have one in every of the best chew forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing 55 to 143 pounds. Present in South East Asia. 8 to 10-inch lengthy tongue for slurping up insects and honey. □□ Location: The Solar bear is discovered within the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It's the least studied bear and. Its population is uncertain however considered vulnerable and on the decline attributable to lack of habitat and poaching. Solar bears are hunted for their gallbladders and other physique parts utilized in conventional medicines. □□ Size: They stand solely 39 to fifty five inches and weigh 55 to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. □□ Features: Solar bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a brief snout. They're named for his or her pale, horseshoe-shaped chest patch that looks like a rising sun. Additionally they eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. □□ Food plan: Sun bears tear apart timber and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." In reality, they have an extremely long tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. □□ Dangerous? As a consequence of its shy nature, attacks are uncommon. Long, shaggy fur and mane gave them the identify sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. □□ Location: The Sloth bear is found within the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining inhabitants of less than 20,000, they are thought of weak. □□ Measurement: They're fifty five to 75 inches long and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. □□ Features: With their lengthy shaggy fur and mane, they're straightforward to tell apart from other Asiatic bears. In actuality, they're very fast and may out-gallop humans. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging the wrong way up from trees. They are noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their large curved claws. □□ Food plan: Their diet consists of termites, ants, and fruit. □□ Dangerous? They are one of the crucial aggressive bears, with essentially the most attacks on humans, principally on account of surprise encounters. They blow the mud around with massive puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they can be heard 600 ft away. Sloth bears stand their floor if threatened and do not mix properly with rhinos and elephants, often charging at each other when in proximity. Solely South American bear. World's last brief-faced bear. The title "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that look like glasses. This susceptible species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are found within the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. □□ Size: They are mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing 47 to seventy nine inches tall. □□ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's last quick-confronted bear and the one bear native to South America. □□ Features: The title "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings round their eyes that generally look like glasses. They spend most of their time in bushes the place they build nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard valuable fruit and carcasses. □□ Diet: Spectacled bears are largely herbivores with a weight loss program consisting of mostly cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, however they are going to opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. □□ Harmful? Living in remote mountains, these shy bears stands out as the least dangerous of all bear species. Their our bodies are smaller than polar bears but larger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a rare hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that happens in both nature and captivity. Grolar bear conduct is closer to the polar bear. They characteristic the lengthy necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they've been documented stomping toys, much like how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably at the London Zoo in 1859, but haven't been confirmed within the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot however DNA checks have been unable to determine what kind of bear it was. Adorable koalas should not bears, they are burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears both, they are indestructible, microscopic animals that can survive in area. Most bear attacks occur when a bear is startled or protecting their cubs. Purple pandas? They're in their own family which can be nearer cousins with skunks and raccoons than bears. 1. BEWARE OF YOUR

SURROUNDINGS. Look ahead to bear scat and bear tracks that will indicate a bear is close by, through which case you wish to be additional vigilant. Listed below are a few tips you should use to forestall bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies safe. 2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you're right here so they don't by accident startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack. 3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** While you might have nice intentions, a bear is likely to really feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself. 3. **Secure YOUR SCENTED Gadgets (AT CAMP).** For those who see a bear, don't try to approach or feed it. This includes meals, but in addition your toiletries, for instance. Whichever methodology you choose, ensure it's at least 200 toes away from your tent so you don't attract bears to your campsite. 4. **Stay CALM.** For those who meet a bear, don't run. Try to make your self look as huge as attainable, waving your arms above your head. You can even extend a jacket above your head to make yourself look bigger. Lock this stuff in a bear canister or use a bear bag to hang them up in a tree. Don't scream or attempt to scare the bear. 5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A last RESORT).** Speak to it calmly and slowly again away. Full instruction on how to make use of bear spray right here. If the bear is dangerously close (30 ft) or is [pooh bear soft toy](#) charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming slightly downward. 6. **Combat Back.** If all else fails and a bear attacks you, don't play lifeless. Which bear is the largest? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 toes long, and 4.0 to 5.25 feet tall, the most important bear by each measurement and weight is the polar bear. The largest ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Fight again with all of your power and hope that it will again down. Which bear is probably the most dangerous? All bears are harmful if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is understood for the most assaults. When in bear country, it's all the time smart to hold bear spray. It's nicely deserved, especially when cubs are around. Annually there are roughly forty six grizzly attacks, 6 leading to loss of life. In North America, grizzly bears have probably the most fearsome status. Which bear is the strongest? Whereas you're most prone to see an American black bear, on average there is only one attack per year. In terms of uncooked chunk energy, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chew reigns supreme. All bears are robust and to not be messed with. When using the chew force quotient (chunk power relative to dimension), the sun bear packs essentially the most punch. Originally named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub found within the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to flee the fireplace however sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Soon after he grew to become an icon and to this present day is the star of the longest-working public service announcement campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear recognized for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. Extra importantly Yogi Bear has impressed numerous thru-hikers to try and grasp the artwork of "yogi-ing", the act of not quite begging however receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, though he has some characteristics of the Asian black bear. He is an easygoing, friendly bear who lives a accountability-free lifestyle. He also is perhaps the first bear to obtain his pilot's license. Before he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son typically would visit on the London Zoo. Winnie is short for "Winnipeg," the city in Canada near the place he was from. Chris additionally wrote The way to Hike the Appalachian Trail. Equal components backpacking meals and ultralight gear. After through-hiking the Appalachian Path, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to supply fast, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic suggestions, guides and the way-to's in your inbox every two weeks.

